

Supplement Tables and Figures

Table S1. List of eligible diagnosis codes to identify iron overload patients based on diagnosis.2

Table S2. List of eligible osteoporosis fractures.....3

Table S1. List of eligible diagnosis codes to identify iron overload patients based on diagnosis.

D104500	Beta trait thalassaemia
C350000	Haemochromatosis
D104.00	Thalassaemia
D104811	Beta thalassaemia
D104211	Sickle-cell thalassaemia
D104z00	Thalassaemia NOS
C350.00	Disorders of iron metabolism
D104700	Beta major thalassaemia
D104000	Thalassaemia major NEC
D104600	Beta intermedia thalassaemia
D104200	Thalassaemia with haemoglobin S disease
D104900	Delta-beta thalassaemia
C350z00	Disorder of iron metabolism NOS
C350y00	Other specified disorder of iron metabolism
D104011	Thalassaemia major - Cooley's anaemia

Table S2. List of eligible osteoporosis fractures	
read_code	medcode_description
Hip Fractures	
S30..00	Fracture of neck of femur
S30..11	Hip fracture
S30y.00	Closed fracture of neck of femur NOS
S30y.11	Hip fracture NOS
7K1L400	Closed reduction of fracture of hip
S302400	Closed fracture of femur, intertrochanteric
7K1L500	Closed reduction of fracture of femur
S302.00	Closed fracture of proximal femur, pertrochanteric
S305.00	Subtrochanteric fracture
S300500	Closed # prox femur, subcapital, Garden grade unspec.
S4E..00	Fracture-dislocation or subluxation hip
S30w.00	Closed fracture of unspecified proximal femur
S300000	Closed # prox femur, intracapsular section, unspecified
S302000	Closed # proximal femur, trochanteric section, unspecified
S4E0.00	Closed fracture-dislocation, hip joint
S300400	Closed fracture head of femur
S300.00	Closed fracture proximal femur, transcervical
S304.00	Pertrochanteric fracture
S300311	Closed fracture, base of neck of femur
S300600	Closed fracture proximal femur, subcapital, Garden grade I
S302200	Closed fracture proximal femur, subtrochanteric
S30z.00	Open fracture of neck of femur NOS
S303400	Open fracture of femur, intertrochanteric
S302100	Closed fracture proximal femur, intertrochanteric, two part
S300300	Closed fracture proximal femur, basicervical
S300900	Closed fracture proximal femur, subcapital, Garden grade IV
S300A00	Closed fracture of femur, upper epiphysis
S302012	Closed fracture of femur, lesser trochanter

S300800	Closed fracture proximal femur, subcapital, Garden grade III
S300y00	Closed fracture proximal femur, other transcervical
S300y11	Closed fracture of femur, subcapital
S300700	Closed fracture proximal femur, subcapital, Garden grade II
S300z00	Closed fracture proximal femur, transcervical, NOS
S302z00	Closed # of proximal femur, pertrochanteric section, NOS
S301500	Open fracture proximal femur,subcapital, Garden grade unspec
S303.00	Open fracture of proximal femur, pertrochanteric
S30x.00	Open fracture of unspecified proximal femur
S301000	Open # proximal femur, intracapsular section, unspecified
S303000	Open # of proximal femur, trochanteric section, unspecified
S4E2.00	Closed fracture-subluxation, hip joint
S300200	Closed fracture proximal femur, midcervical section
S301900	Open fracture proximal femur,subcapital, Garden grade IV
S4E1.00	Open fracture-dislocation, hip joint
S301600	Open fracture proximal femur,subcapital, Garden grade I
S300100	Closed fracture proximal femur, transepiphyseal
S303z00	Open fracture of proximal femur, pertrochanteric, NOS
S303200	Open fracture proximal femur, subtrochanteric
S301700	Open fracture proximal femur,subcapital, Garden grade II
S301y00	Open fracture proximal femur, other transcervical
S301100	Open fracture proximal femur, transepiphyseal
S301400	Open fracture head, femur
S301A00	Open fracture of femur, upper epiphysis
S303011	Open fracture of femur, greater trochanter
S303100	Open fracture proximal femur, intertrochanteric, two part
S301800	Open fracture proximal femur,subcapital, Garden grade III
S301y11	Open fracture of femur, subcapital
S301.00	Open fracture proximal femur, transcervical
S303300	Open fracture proximal femur, intertrochanteric, comminuted
S301311	Open fracture base of neck of femur
S13..00	Fracture or disruption of pelvis

S130.00	Closed fracture acetabulum
S10B500	Fracture of pubis
S132.00	Closed fracture pubis
S132100	Closed fracture pelvis, multiple pubic rami - stable
S132000	Closed fracture pelvis, single pubic ramus
S10B400	Fracture of acetabulum
S134z00	Other or multiple closed fracture of pelvis NOS
S108.00	Closed fracture pelvis, coccyx
S134600	Closed fracture pelvis, iliac wing
S10B300	Fracture of ilium
S134400	Closed fracture pelvis, anterior superior iliac spine
S13y.00	Closed fracture of pelvis NOS
S132z00	Closed fracture pubis NOS
S134.00	Other or multiple closed fracture of pelvis
S134800	Closed fracture dislocation of sacro-iliac joint
S4J2100	Closed fracture-subluxation of pelvis
S133000	Open fracture pelvis, single pubic ramus
S134100	Closed fracture pelvis, ischium
S4J0100	Closed fracture-dislocation of pelvis
S135z00	Other/multiple open fracture of pelvis NOS
S132y00	Other specified closed fracture pubis
S134500	Closed fracture pelvis, anterior inferior iliac spine
S134000	Closed fracture of ilium, unspecified
S134300	Closed fracture pelvis, ischial tuberosity
S135400	Open fracture pelvis, anterior superior iliac spine
S4J1100	Open fracture-dislocation of pelvis
S130z00	Closed fracture acetabulum NOS
S132200	Closed fracture pelvis, multiple pubic rami - unstable
S133.00	Open fracture of pubis
S133100	Open fracture pelvis, multiple pubic rami - stable
S131.00	Open fracture acetabulum
S130300	Closed fracture acetabulum, posterior column

S130y00	Other specified closed fracture acetabulum
S131y00	Other specified open fracture acetabulum
S13z.00	Open fracture of pelvis NOS
S131z00	Open fracture acetabulum NOS
S135.00	Other or multiple open fracture of pelvis
S4J3100	Open fracture-subluxation of pelvis
S135600	Open fracture pelvis, iliac wing
S135300	Open fracture pelvis, ischial tuberosity
S130400	Closed fracture acetabulum, floor
S133z00	Open fracture of pubis NOS
S130000	Closed fracture acetabulum, anterior lip alone
S130200	Closed fracture acetabulum, anterior column
S133y00	Other specified open fracture of pubis
S130100	Closed fracture acetabulum, posterior lip alone
S135800	Open fracture dislocation of sacro-iliac joint
S135000	Open fracture of ilium, unspecified
Clinical Vertebral Fractures	
S10x.00	Closed fracture of spine, unspecified,
N331.12	Collapse of vertebra NOS
S104.00	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra
S15..00	Fracture of thoracic vertebra
S104100	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, wedge
S10B200	Fracture of coccyx
S10..00	Fracture of spine without mention of spinal cord injury
S10..12	Fracture of vertebra without spinal cord lesion
N331F00	Collapse of thoracic vertebra
N331G00	Collapse of lumbar vertebra
S102.00	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra
S100.00	Closed fracture of cervical spine
S10B000	Fracture of lumbar vertebra
S102100	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra, wedge
N331800	Osteoporosis + pathological fracture lumbar vertebrae

S106.00	Closed fracture sacrum
N331900	Osteoporosis + pathological fracture thoracic vertebrae
S150.00	Multiple fractures of thoracic spine
S10B100	Fracture of sacrum
N1y1.00	Fatigue fracture of vertebra
N331K00	Collapse of thoracic vertebra due to osteoporosis
N331J00	Collapse of lumbar vertebra due to osteoporosis
N331L00	Collapse of vertebra due to osteoporosis NOS
7J41.00	Decompression of fracture of spine
S100000	Closed fracture of unspecified cervical vertebra
S10B600	Multiple fractures of lumbar spine and pelvis
S10A200	Multiple fractures of cervical spine
7J43.00	Fixation of fracture of spine
S10..11	Fracture of transverse process spine - no spinal cord lesion
S10B.00	Fracture of lumbar spine and pelvis
N331E00	Collapse of cervical vertebra
S10z.00	Fracture of spine without mention of spinal cord lesion NOS
7J42.00	Other reduction of fracture of spine
N331D00	Collapsed vertebra NOS
N331100	Pathological fracture of lumbar vertebra
S100200	Closed fracture axis
S11..00	Fracture of spine with spinal cord lesion
S104400	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, transverse process
N331H00	Collapse of cervical vertebra due to osteoporosis
S10A100	Fracture of second cervical vertebra
N331.14	Osteoporotic vertebral collapse
S100211	C2 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
S100700	Closed fracture of seventh cervical vertebra
S100A00	Closed fracture axis, odontoid process
S100600	Closed fracture of sixth cervical vertebra
S102z00	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra not otherwise specified
S100500	Closed fracture of fifth cervical vertebra

N331011	Collapse of thoracic vertebra
N331111	Collapse of lumbar vertebra
S104000	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, burst
S10A000	Fracture of first cervical vertebra
S100711	C7 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
S11x.00	Closed fracture of spine with spinal cord lesion unspecified
S100611	C6 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
S100z00	Closed fracture of cervical spine not otherwise specified
S102y00	Other specified closed fracture thoracic vertebra
S100111	C1 vertebra closed fracture - no spinal cord lesion
S105.00	Open fracture lumbar vertebra
7J42.11	Other reduction of fracture of spine and stabilisation
S11..12	Fracture of vertebra with spinal cord lesion
S100511	C5 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
S100400	Closed fracture of fourth cervical vertebra
S100K00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, spinous process
S100300	Closed fracture of third cervical vertebra
S100H00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, wedge
S116.00	Closed fracture of sacrum with spinal cord lesion
S100411	C4 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
N331A00	Osteoporosis + pathological fracture cervical vertebrae
S102000	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra, burst
7J42100	Open reduction of fracture of spine NEC
S100x00	Multiple closed fractures of cervical vertebrae
S104300	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, spinous process
S102400	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra, transverse process
S100311	C3 vertebra closed fracture without spinal cord lesion
S100L00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, transverse process
S100D00	Closed fracture axis, transverse process
S101.00	Open fracture of cervical spine
S106000	Closed compression fracture sacrum
S103.00	Open fracture thoracic vertebra

S102300	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra, spinous process
S103100	Open fracture thoracic vertebra, wedge
S100C00	Closed fracture axis, spinous process
S109.00	Open fracture pelvis, coccyx
S104200	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, spondylolysis
S10y.00	Open fracture of spine, unspecified,
S101111	C1 vertebra open fracture without spinal cord lesion
S11..11	Fracture of transverse process of spine + spinal cord lesion
S106100	Closed vertical fracture of sacrum
S104600	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, tricolunar
S101600	Open fracture of sixth cervical vertebra
Syu1500	[X]Fracture of other specified cervical vertebra
S104500	Closed fracture lumbar vertebra, posterior arch
N331.11	Collapse of spine NOS
S105100	Open fracture lumbar vertebra, wedge
S107.00	Open fracture sacrum
S100G00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, burst
S100900	Closed fracture atlas, comminuted
S105000	Open fracture lumbar vertebra, burst
S101211	C2 vertebra open fracture without spinal cord lesion
S101500	Open fracture of fifth cervical vertebra
S101711	C7 vertebra open fracture without spinal cord lesion
S101611	C6 vertebra open fracture without spinal cord lesion
S101100	Open fracture atlas
S101x00	Multiple open fractures of cervical vertebrae
S100M00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, posterior arch
S100J00	Closed fracture cervical vertebra, spondylolysis
S102200	Closed fracture thoracic vertebra, spondylolysis
S101200	Open fracture axis
S101A00	Open fracture axis, odontoid process
S100E00	Closed fracture axis, posterior arch
S107100	Open vertical fracture of sacrum

S134700	Closed vertical fracture of ilium
Humerus Fractures	
S22..00	Fracture of humerus
S2...00	Fracture of upper limb
S228.00	Fracture of lower end of humerus
S224100	Closed fracture distal humerus, supracondylar
S220.00	Closed fracture of the proximal humerus
S224.11	Elbow fracture - closed
7K11E00	Closed reduction of fracture of elbow
S28z.00	Ill-defined fractures of upper limb NOS
S22z.00	Fracture of humerus NOS
S226.00	Fracture of upper end of humerus
7K11F00	Closed reduction of fracture of humerus
S220100	Closed fracture proximal humerus, neck
S224.00	Closed fracture of the distal humerus
S2z..00	Fracture of upper limb NOS
S4B..00	Fracture-dislocation or subluxation elbow
S224700	Closed fracture distal humerus, medial epicondyle
S224600	Closed fracture distal humerus, lateral epicondyle
S220300	Closed fracture proximal humerus, greater tuberosity
S225.11	Elbow fracture - open
S224000	Closed fracture of elbow, unspecified part
S227.00	Fracture of shaft of humerus
S224200	Closed fracture distal humerus, lateral condyle
S222000	Closed fracture of humerus NOS
S222100	Closed fracture of humerus, shaft
S220000	Closed fracture of proximal humerus, unspecified part
S4B0.00	Closed fracture-dislocation elbow
S220400	Closed fracture proximal humerus, head
S225100	Open fracture distal humerus, supracondylar
S224800	Closed fracture distal humerus, capitellum
S302011	Closed fracture of femur, greater trochanter

S222.00	Closed fracture of humerus, shaft or unspecified part
S224300	Closed fracture distal humerus, medial condyle
S225.00	Open fracture of the distal humerus
S224z00	Closed fracture of distal humerus, not otherwise specified
S221.00	Open fracture of the proximal humerus
S220z00	Closed fracture of proximal humerus not otherwise specified
S220200	Closed fracture of proximal humerus, anatomical neck
S4B0000	Closed fracture-dislocation elbow joint
S224400	Closed fracture of distal humerus, condyle(s) unspecified
S220500	Closed fracture of humerus, upper epiphysis
S225700	Open fracture distal humerus, medial epicondyle
S225600	Open fracture distal humerus, lateral epicondyle
S220700	Closed fracture proximal humerus, four part
S223000	Open fracture of humerus NOS
S224500	Closed fracture of distal humerus, trochlea
S225200	Open fracture distal humerus, lateral condyle
S225000	Open fracture of elbow, unspecified part
S222z00	Closed fracture of humerus, shaft or unspecified part NOS
S225800	Open fracture distal humerus, capitellum
S223.00	Open fracture of humerus, shaft or unspecified part
S223100	Open fracture of humerus, shaft
S4B2.00	Closed fracture-subluxation elbow
S302300	Closed # proximal femur, intertrochanteric, comminuted
S221300	Open fracture proximal humerus, greater tuberosity
S221100	Open fracture proximal humerus, neck
S224x00	Closed fracture of distal humerus, multiple
S224900	Closed fracture distal humerus, bicondylar (T-Y fracture)
S4B2000	Closed fracture-subluxation elbow joint
S225z00	Open fracture of distal humerus, not otherwise specified
S221000	Open fracture of proximal humerus, unspecified part
S225300	Open fracture distal humerus, medial condyle
S221z00	Open fracture of proximal humerus not otherwise specified

S221400	Open fracture proximal humerus, head
S223z00	Open fracture of humerus, shaft or unspecified part NOS
S225500	Open fracture of distal humerus, trochlea
S221600	Open fracture proximal humerus, three part
S221200	Open fracture of proximal humerus, anatomical neck
S221500	Open fracture of humerus, upper epiphysis
S225400	Open fracture of distal humerus, condyle(s) unspecified
S221700	Open fracture proximal humerus, four part
S4B3.00	Open fracture-subluxation elbow
S225900	Open fracture distal humerus, bicondylar (T-Y fracture)
S225x00	Open fracture of distal humerus, multiple
Forearm Fractures	
S23x111	Fracture of radius NOS
S234100	Closed Colles' fracture
S234.11	Wrist fracture - closed
S23..00	Fracture of radius and ulna
S23B.00	Fracture of lower end of radius
S234200	Closed fracture of the distal radius, unspecified
S23x100	Closed fracture of radius (alone), unspecified
7K1LL00	Closed reduction of fracture of radius and or ulna
S23x211	Fracture of ulna NOS
S230600	Closed fracture radius, head
S2...11	Arm fracture
S23z.00	Fracture of radius and ulna, NOS
S23x300	Closed fracture of the radius and ulna
S237.00	Fracture of upper end of radius
S234.00	Closed fracture of radius and ulna, lower end
S239.00	Fracture of shaft of radius
S234B00	Closed fracture radial styloid
S28..11	Ill-defined fracture of arm
S23..11	Forearm fracture
S234300	Closed fracture of ulna, styloid process

S234700	Closed Smith's fracture
S238.00	Fracture of shaft of ulna
S23x200	Closed fracture of ulna (alone), unspecified
S230700	Closed fracture radius, neck
S234600	Closed fracture radius and ulna, distal
S4C..00	Fracture-dislocation or subluxation of wrist
S235.11	Wrist fracture - open
S23C.00	Fracture of lower end of both ulna and radius
S234z00	Closed fracture of forearm, lower end, NOS
S232.00	Closed fracture of radius and ulna, shaft
S235100	Open Colles' fracture
S230.00	Closed fracture of proximal radius and ulna
S234500	Closed fracture distal ulna, unspecified
S23x.00	Closed fracture of radius and ulna, unspecified part
S293.00	Multiple fractures of forearm
S232100	Closed fracture of the radial shaft
S230300	Closed Monteggia's fracture
S23A.00	Fracture of shafts of both ulna and radius
S230900	Closed fracture of the proximal radius
S236.00	Fracture of upper end of ulna
S234000	Closed fracture of forearm, lower end, unspecified
S231600	Open fracture radial head
S230200	Closed fracture of ulna, coronoid
S232200	Closed fracture of the ulnar shaft
S4C0.00	Closed fracture dislocation of wrist
S23xz00	Closed fracture of radius and ulna, NOS
S234E00	Closed fracture distal radius, intra-articular, other type
S232000	Closed fracture of radius, shaft, unspecified
S234900	Closed volar Barton's fracture
S232300	Closed fracture radius and ulna, middle
S235200	Open fracture of the distal radius, unspecified
S23x000	Closed fracture of forearm, unspecified

S232z00	Closed fracture of radius and ulna, shaft, NOS
S234800	Closed Galeazzi fracture
S4C0000	Closed fracture-dislocation distal radio-ulnar joint
S230711	Closed # radius neck
S234D00	Closed fracture distal radius, extra-articular, other type
S235B00	Open fracture radial styloid
S231700	Open fracture radial neck
S230500	Closed fracture of the proximal ulna
S230A00	Closed fracture radius and ulna, proximal
S23y100	Open fracture of radius (alone), unspecified
S233.00	Open fracture of radius and ulna, shaft
S230000	Closed fracture of proximal forearm, unspecified part
S231300	Open Monteggia's fracture
S230z00	Closed fracture of proximal forearm not otherwise specified
S235700	Open Smith's fracture
S220600	Closed fracture proximal humerus, three part
S235600	Open fracture radius and ulna, distal
S23y.00	Open fracture of radius and ulna, unspecified part
S235300	Open fracture of ulna, styloid process
S234111	Smith's fracture - closed
S234400	Closed fracture of ulna, lower epiphysis
S23y200	Open fracture of ulna (alone), unspecified
S4C2000	Closed fracture-subluxation, distal radio-ulnar jt
S23y300	Open fracture of the radius and ulna
S231.00	Open fracture of proximal radius and ulna
S234A00	Closed dorsal Barton's fracture
S234C00	Closed fracture distal radius, intra-articular, die-punch
S230800	Closed fracture proximal radius, comminuted
S235900	Open volar Barton's fracture
S23yz00	Open fracture of radius and ulna, NOS
S233200	Open fracture of the ulnar shaft
S233z00	Open fracture of radius and ulna, shaft, NOS

S235800	Open Galeazzi fracture
S233000	Open fracture of radius, shaft, unspecified
S233100	Open fracture of the radial shaft
S233300	Open fracture radius and ulna, middle
S235000	Open fracture of forearm, lower end, unspecified
S23y000	Open fracture of forearm, unspecified
S235z00	Open fracture of forearm, lower end, NOS
S231A00	Open fracture radius and ulna, proximal
S235500	Open fracture distal ulna - other
S235E00	Open fracture distal radius, intra-articular other type
S4C1000	Open fracture-dislocation, distal radio-ulnar joint
S230400	Closed fracture of proximal ulna, comminuted
S231500	Open fracture of the proximal ulna
S4B0100	Closed fracture-dislocation superior radio-ulnar joint
S231200	Open fracture of ulna, coronoid
S4C3000	Open fracture-subluxation, distal radio-ulnar joint
S235D00	Open fracture distal radius, extra-articular other type
S231900	Open fracture of the proximal radius
S231000	Open fracture of proximal forearm, unspecified
S234911	Closed volar Barton's fracture-dislocation
S231z00	Open fracture of forearm, upper end, NOS
S234912	Closed volar Barton fracture-subluxation
S234A11	Closed dorsal Barton's fracture-dislocation
S235400	Open fracture of ulna, lower epiphysis
S231800	Open fracture proximal radius, comminuted
S230100	Closed fracture olecranon, extra-articular
S230B00	Closed fracture olecranon, intra-articular
S231B00	Open fracture olecranon, intra-articular
S2A..00	Fracture of upper limb, level unspecified
7K1LN00	Closed reduction of fracture of upper limb
S280.00	Closed ill-defined fractures of upper limb
S28..00	Ill-defined fractures of upper limb

S281.00	Open ill-defined fractures of upper limb
S234F00	Closed Barton's fracture
S235F00	Open Barton's fracture